

The coloniality of English proficiency and EMI: Decolonization, language equity, and epistemic (in)justice

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The widely publicized 2015 #FeesMustFall student protests in South Africa (SA) have foregrounded concerns about social justice, epistemic justice, access to higher education, and decolonization of the curriculum, and language. This paper critiques the English as a medium of instruction (EMI) policy and a monolingual English language proficiency (ELP) curriculum in a university and suggests strategies for epistemic decolonization. The article is based on the locus of enunciation of the author, and the analysis of language curriculum documents. It draws on epistemologies of the South and decolonial perspectives to answer two questions: What are the prospects of decolonizing EMI in Higher Education? How can English language proficiency be decolonized? The article argues that English proficiency is anchored by epistemic racism, Anglocentric ideologies and an inequitable policy of EMI, and the continued disregard for multilingualism in higher education. It proposes that decolonization strategies are necessary to enhance epistemic justice, reduce inequality and transform the EMI and ELP in South African higher education. This can be done through English as a multilingua franca and solidarity-based epistemologies, such as Ubuntu-Neplanta.

Keywords: Coloniality; Decoloniality; English Proficiency; Epistemicides; Epistemic Justice; Epistemic Racism; Medium of Instruction

1. Introduction

Decolonization is a term that is ubiquitous in the South African higher education landscape. The student protests over #FeesMustFall, and #RhodesMustFall in 2015/2016 have resulted in sustained decolonization conversations in the SA higher education sector and have made academics rethink the meaning¹ of transformation, decolonization, and re-curriculation processes, (e.g., Le Grange, 2018). Almost all aspects of universities have not been spared by advocates of decolonization. This is seen in the growing literature on decolonization, for example, the decolonization of the curriculum (Le Grange, 2018), and the decolonization of the university (Mbembe, 2016).

However, none of the discussions have addressed the complex challenge of undoing the coloniality of English as a medium of instruction (EMI) and English

language proficiency (ELP) in order to attain epistemic justice and language equity. Epistemic justice is a concept that is gaining popularity amongst decolonial scholarship. For example, Stroud and Kerfoot (2020) explain that “pursuing epistemic justice means ‘going beyond’ colonialities of language, and critically engaging with contemporary ideas of multilingualism and the very notion of language itself” (p. 3). In South Africa, my observation is that EMI is established through institutional policies and epistemic injustices, while ELP is part of the ‘practice’ within a discipline in the university offered by English Studies departments, academic development programs, and similar units. In most universities in South Africa (SA), ELP consists of courses such as English language proficiency (ELP), English for Academic Purposes (EAP), Academic Literacy, and so on.

Both EMI and ELP within the university and the discipline of English studies perpetuate coloniality, epistemicides, and epistemic racism. Epistemic racism is in white Euro-American values, beliefs, and so on dominating the world through colonialism, capitalism, and neo-colonialism, (Kubota, 2019). Epistemicides are actions that use EMI to erase multilingualism and create linguistic injustices (Phyak, 2021). EMI uses monolingualism as a norm to the exclusion of any other language. In addition, epistemicides are actions that silence knowledge produced in the Global South (Santos 2020). Epistemicides and coloniality are persistent problems in former colonies, postcolonial, and post-apartheid societies where the dominance of imperial English threatens national objectives of increasing access, reducing linguistics inequality, and transforming the curriculum (e.g., Parmegiani, 2012; Stroud & Kerfoot, 2020).

For instance, in South Africa, Parmegiani (2012) describes how a lack of proficiency in English excludes some from education, and employment. Hence, Stroud and Kerfoot (2020) explore alternative ways of rethinking language and multilingualism to promote epistemic justice. They observe that the continuation of apartheid-era language policies of giving more power to English and, to a limited extent Afrikaans, has maintained the status quo in South Africa. This paper argues that epistemologies of the South can reframe language and multilingualism and therefore should be invoked by academics to decolonize language policies and language education in order to attain epistemic justice.

As the author of this article, I have grappled for many years over the complex relationship between the beliefs and policies of academics at my university and the actual practices that are implemented through the curriculum, syllabus, teaching, and learning processes. This has made me realize that decolonization, transformation of the curriculum and disciplines, and the entire system of higher education has to filter down to the academic departments. I draw on

epistemologies of the South to dismantle the colonial epistemicides/epistemic violence (Heleta, 2016; Pillay, 2015) in English Studies and language policies. South Africa has a long history of colonialism that spans centuries which was intensified through apartheid in the 20th century. Both colonialism and apartheid have left an indelible mark on Higher Education. This article will only focus on a critique of academics and is therefore limited in addressing the entirety of the intellectual struggle for decolonization because it does not include students, professional staff, administrative staff, and the stakeholders who all form part of the university.

Decoloniality should include practical changes and actions to address curriculum, university, English, education, policies, and so on. Therefore, the main problem is in the implementation of an EMI policy and the configuration of a discipline of ELP curriculum, and it results in the continuity of coloniality and epistemicides in the academic department (cf. Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2022a, 2022b). Likewise, Makhanya and Zibane (2020) describe the epistemological impediments of university students in non-multilingual class engagements. They show how access to education is hindered by the limited use of indigenous languages.

This paper is based on my self-reflexivity² as a Senior Lecturer in the Department of English Studies, at the University of South Africa (Unisa). In this paper, I critique a unique epistemic injustice that is skills-based, instrumental, and neoliberal but often disguises itself as social justice, and access. These epistemic injustices are perpetuated by all races, e.g., both 'Blacks' and Whites, and others in South Africa. The paper focusses on decolonizing the English discipline through EMI policies and curriculum principles of language content, e.g., ELP syllabus. Content in this paper denotes English Language Proficiency and the EMI policy; both of these are entangled with epistemicides, and coloniality, and they show its pervasiveness in the institution and in the English Departments specifically (e.g., Chaka 2021; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2022a, 2022b). I argue that for decoloniality to be effective, both curriculum and policy have to be reconceptualized.

The paper is organized in the following sequence: starting with situating the problem in EMI and ELP, it moves to describe some of the cracks and fissures of decolonization. I then discuss the theoretical framework under the title: *Onto-Epistemologies of the South* and some decolonial options. I then critique the current epistemicides and coloniality of English Language Proficiency and EMI. Furthermore, I pose a question: What should Language proficiency entail? In the denouement, I raise some glimmer of hope towards decolonizing EMI and ELP: *English as a Multilingual Franca* and *Ubuntu-Neplanta*, and in the conclusion, I advance to decolonial options in the form of a manifesto.

2. Locating the problem in both EMI and an imperial ELP as a discipline

The 2020 language policy framework for the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) seeks to promote multilingualism. Multilingualism is defined in the policy as the use and promotion of multiple languages. The policy articulates that in addition to English, all official languages must be eligible for institutional language policies (DHET, 2020). On the other hand, the language policy of the University of South Africa (Unisa) states that the language(s) of learning and teaching in all undergraduate courses will be English with ‘scaffolding’ in other official languages, (Unisa, 2016). When read in the context of the policy, the word ‘scaffolding’ appears to be suggesting that some support should be conducted in the other official languages.³

Currently, Unisa is the only dedicated Open Distance eLearning (ODEL) institution in the country. ODeL is described in a policy of Unisa (2018) as learning that is mediated through a range of current and emerging digital technologies and Open Distance Learning is defined as a: “multi-dimensional concept aimed at bridging the time, geographical, economic, social, educational and communication distance between student and institution, student and academics, student and courseware, and student and peers” (p. 2). Part of Unisa’s mission is to grant open access to a diverse profile of students who would traditionally not be accepted by some of the public face-to-face universities. In terms of enrolment numbers, it can be assumed that the university is granting access, with an enrolment that was around 373,700 in 2023 (Unisa, 2023). However, there is little evidence in the entire university of decoloniality, language equity, and epistemic justice.

As a consequence of the #FeesMustFall protests, Unisa introduced a series of decolonial summer schools between 2014 to 2020. The aim of the summer schools was to “un-learn some of the toxic ‘un-truths’ that the Euro-Western education system” (Segalo, 2020, p. 49) has brought to academics, to produce critical thinkers, able to critique disciplines and start to rethink how they teach and understand knowledge production. One of the themes of the summer school was decolonising the university. This theme resonates with the focus of this paper.

English performs multiple socio-political functions in Higher Education. In fact, the relationship between politics and language in SA has attracted a lot of attention (Mwaniki, 2018; Parmegiani, 2012). For example, many people still conflate being educated with speaking English. Van Pinxteren (2022) challenges the taken for granted assumption that decolonizing the curriculum can go ahead without considering the medium of instruction. He argues that “an evolution towards education for the masses (not the elite) will of necessity

be accompanied by an evolution towards an Indigenous medium of instruction” (p. 88).

Several scholars have argued that higher education in South Africa is dominated by English as a medium of instruction, as a result of the colonial and imperial history (e.g., Hurst 2016; Motsa, 2017). The constitution of SA recognizes 11 official languages, and all public universities are required to implement multilingualism (Government of South Africa, 1996). However, multilingualism is not embraced by academics, and the hegemony of English is perpetuated through English as a medium of instruction and through the historical position of English studies in ensuring that it supports the requirements for proficiency in English in various domains of higher education (cf. Heleta 2016). English acts as a gatekeeper (rather than access) and proficiency in English is linked to academic success, although there is no evidence to back some of the beliefs. This is despite the fact that in SA, educational inequality is deeply entrenched in historic disadvantages associated with some universities and a poor quality of teaching in schools.

The complexity of English as a gatekeeper on the one hand, and as a medium of instruction is further exacerbated by the attitudes and beliefs of academics in the institution at large and those who teach English. Maseko and Mgutshini (2020) argue that English Language proficiency results in gradueness, employability, social mobility, as well as global citizenry. In their view, no other language/African language is able to bring such returns (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a). They assert that their views are transformative and are from a critical emancipatory perspective (Maseko & Mgutshini, 2020). This shows that even when we are all located in the Global South and within the same institution, what counts as ‘critical research’, and transformation can be contested. Another problem with Maseko and Mgutshini’s (2020) argument is claiming that the low throughput rate, especially at Unisa, is because English is not the first language for the majority of the students, yet there is insufficient research that has been conducted to prove that indeed first language speakers of English are outperforming second language speakers.

Access to higher education is relatively low in SA amongst black students, and that is why it was part of the protests by students for decolonizing the university and #FeesMustFall. Pennycook and Makoni (2020) mention that it is only 20% of black students who are in higher education, and that institutions have not accommodated and decolonized to a point where they are able to handle black students within the universities. In addition, a majority of black students have to deal with the challenge of monolingual policies and ELP which impedes them from access and epistemic justice.

3. Current cracks and fissures in decolonizing English Language Teaching and the EMI

There are dissenting views on how to decolonize language in the university, in relation to English as a medium of instruction (EMI). Some scholars (e.g., Makhanya & Zibane, 2020; Prah, 2018) suggest the use of African languages as a means of decolonization and Africanization, (e.g., Motsa, 2017; Potgieter & Anthonissen, 2017). Motsa (2017) laments the fact that African languages like isiZulu are viewed as incapable of transmitting scientific and educational knowledge while English is “the sole vehicle of knowledge transmission, communication and research in the colonies” (p. 31).

The EMI in universities has remained English long after the end of colonialism, and apartheid in South Africa (Heleta, 2016). According to Davis (2017), Mamdani says that the legacy of this policy remains with us today, leading to a situation where it is not possible to speak of academic thinkers who are rooted in African epistemologies and languages (Davis, 2017).

There is a prevailing assumption that all South African learners should attain sufficient levels of English proficiency (Potgieter & Anthonissen, 2017). Therefore, in a majority of schools, learners get exposed to English for about 10 to 12 years before reaching university, but this does not guarantee mastery of English even where English is the medium of instruction. Statistically only 12% of South Africans use English as a Home language (Statistics SA). Although, there are beliefs about the importance of English as an international language and as a language of the knowledge, economy, development, and upward mobility within the society, English does not give access, but it excludes the majority who are Blacks in SA (Van Broakhuizen et al., 2016).

The epistemic injustices in English proficiency are seen in the strong perceptions/beliefs in the EMI. For instance, Ngcobo and Barnes (2021) investigated the perceptions of the Language of Learning and Teaching (LoLT) and EMI in order to include students as the real stakeholders in the policy implementation process. Students showed a resounding preference of English even though the language poses challenges to them. This finding is contrary to the fact that most of them are non-mother tongue speakers of English, and they struggle to comprehend course material at Unisa.

The concerns of access and transformation in higher education have highlighted the question of language (e.g., Makhanya & Zibane, 2020; Mkhize, 2018). Mkhize (2018) correctly observes that the language question is central to ensuring educational access and social justice, but that it remains largely unresolved after the 2015 protests. I draw on epistemologies of the South, for example, Escobar (2016) who advances the relationality and interconnectivity

that can come about if the critical gaze is on the investigation of knowledge, the pluriverse (Santos, 2018, 2020), and away from epistemic coloniality.

4. Theoretical framework: Onto-epistemologies of the South and some decolonial options

The epistemologies of the South consist of both theoretical and methodological approaches with a negative and positive dimension. The negative deconstructs Eurocentric roots, while the positive dimension produces other kinds of ecologies of knowledges, and validates non-scientific and artisanal knowledges. Santos (2020) argues that theories produced by Eurocentric social sciences are ethno-theories; they produce and reproduce abyssal lines between metropolitan sociability and colonial sociability, by making them invisible at the same time (cf. Santos, 2018). Santos outlines some of the cognitive injustices that are signaled by the colonial abyssal line separating the colonial West and the colonized South. The reason why an onto-epistemological framework is needed is precisely because of an “ontological turn” (Escobar, 2016, p.22). Epistemologies of the South are able to question the ecologies of knowledge between what is known and the knower, knowledge, and reality, (cf. Savransky, 2017).

As mentioned above, because of the complex nature of EMI and ELP in my context, I draw on ontologies and epistemologies of the South in order to arrive at some ‘decolonial options’ (Mignolo & Walsh, 2018). Ontologies of language have received less attention in my context of both monolingualism and multilingualism. As Singh (2017) observes, the “study of language and literature is precisely the study of how language escapes, evades, and crystallizes differently at different times and through different speakers” (pp. 89-90). Singh’s view is important because of the epistemologies that are often invisible in the study of language. Santos (2018) describes the epistemicides of modern science as that which translates into normative dualisms such as truth/falsity or knowledge/opinion. Furthermore, Ndhlovu and Kelly (2020) observe that there are several aspects of epistemicides obtained from Euro-modernity. These are Christian modernity, modern nation-state ideologies, and technologies of orthography and orthodoxy. Epistemicides include “linguicism” (Skutnabb-Kangas, 1988, as cited in Higgins, 2009, p. 8), and those related to language teaching such as standards, native speakerism, and language and nation (e.g., Holliday, 2008). Therefore, epistemologies of the South first reveal the epistemicides in both EMI and ELP in order to advance possible solutions. In other words, they describe both the negative and positive.

One useful concept from the epistemologies of the South is the locus of enunciation. I situate this paper within my locus of enunciation at Unisa, and the epistemologies of the South, (Escobar, 2016; Santos, 2018; Santos & Meneses, 2020). Grosfuguel (2007, as cited in Figueiredo & Martinez, 2021, p. 356) defines the locus of enunciation as the “geo-political and body-political location of the speaking subject.” It means being conscious of and explicit about the geographical, historical, bodily, and ideological context from which one is speaking (Souza, 2019). The locus of enunciation is a counter strategy against the North’s tendency to universalize and its tendency for a ‘God’s eye view’. Sugiharto (2020) describes the locus of enunciation as a resistant tactic, a way of challenging and fighting against coloniality. Another concept that is associated with the locus of enunciation is epistemic decolonization. The process of epistemic decolonization entails turning the critical reflexive gaze ‘inwardly’ because southern scholars are frequently complicit in perpetuating and upholding the epistemic centres of the North (Sugiharto, 2020).

Both the epistemologies of the South and the locus of enunciation are useful theoretical lenses of decolonizing the curriculum, including EMI. Santos (2020) argues that the essence of decolonizing the curriculum is about making the abyssal line visible, to which Escobar (2020) makes a rejoinder that sometimes the line is very deep or extremely undecipherable; therefore, Escobar (2020) draws on both epistemic and ontological decolonization aiming at the abyssal line. Escobar argues that epistemologies of the South are not only about knowledge that comes from academia—such as ratings, rankings, and the university culture. They are ‘relational ontologies’ (Escobar, 2016). Therefore, struggles of the students for access, equity, education, and employment cannot be understood through globalization and internationalization. For instance, there is a proliferation of Eurocentric ways of viewing English as an international language and Global English in the Global South.

Pennycook and Makoni (2020) observe that education is a realm in which languages are regulated and determined. They suggest Ubuntu-Nepantla as a way of thinking about thinking and not as a solution. Ubuntu-Nepantla brings together both Southern African understandings of interdependence and Central American considerations of borderlands. One of the reasons for this is the entanglements between North and South and their inbetweenness. In language “an unstable inbetweenness” appears “rather than firmly bounded entities” (Pennycook and Makoni, 2020, p. 109; see also Ndhlovu & Kelly, 2020). Decolonizing English EMI and ELP, therefore, necessitates a foundational strategy of transformational theorizing to shift our ideological paradigms and the positions from which we imagine solutions (Hsu, 2017).

In this paper, onto-epistemological approaches uncover epistemic injustices and propose the solutions for the two research questions:

1. What are the prospects of decolonizing EMI in Higher Education?
2. How can English Language Proficiency be decolonized?

Drawing on the notion of ‘disinvention and reconstitution’ (Pennycook & Makoni, 2020), I argue that decolonizing EMI and proficiency should result in reconstituting the relationship between English and multilingualism (Makoni & Pennycook, 2007; Rudwick & Makoni, 2021).

5. The epistemicides and coloniality of ELP and EMI

To begin with my locus of enunciation, I am a senior lecturer in the English Studies Department at the University of South Africa (Unisa). In addition, I have been the coordinator for quality assurance of the modules and programs in the Department of English Studies for over five years. The role and mission of an English Studies department in a post-apartheid, postcolonial/decolonial era need to be re-examined. Scholars from the global North identify three strands of English Language Studies. Firstly, the study of English as an additional language is now happening in most Anglophone and non-Anglophone settings, with the two major fields being TESOL and EAP. The second strand is what constitute the study of TESOL or EAP within linguistics, applied linguistics, English education and sometimes literary studies. The third dimension is the research and scholarship on how English is “used as a resource for communication across the variety of human social and cultural engagements, from the local and individual to the international and political” (Seargeant et al., 2018, p. 2-3). These three strands must all be subjected to epistemological and ontological decolonization to guard against coloniality, epistemicides, and epistemic racism.

Proficiency in English is a gatekeeper in higher education (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b, 2021c, 2023b). In a recent systematic review for Europe and Asia, Macaro et al. (2018) identify the lack of research on English language proficiency, EMI, and HE in Africa; for instance, “the concept of ‘proficiency needed to teach through EMI’ is underspecified either through empirical research or by institutional requirements” (p. 65). Some definitions of proficiency originate from the West, or what is referred to as the Global North and find their way in local universities. Countries like the US, UK, and Australia have traditionally been very influential in South African higher education. For example, Fenton-Smith et al. (2018) explore English language proficiency meant for English as an Additional Language (EAL) students at Griffiths University in Australia. Murray (2013) describes proficiency as a general communicative competence in language that enables its users to express and

understand meaning accurately, fluently and appropriately according to context, and comprises a set of generic skills and abilities.

Sebolai (2016) defines English proficiency as the ability to use language in the general sense. It includes speaking, listening, reading, and writing. However, Sebolai (2016) acknowledges that “being proficient in reading and writing a language does not necessarily guarantee competence in the language ability required for coping with the demands of higher education study” (p. 48). There has been a growing recognition that (a) proficiency in English and (b) academic literacies are separate things in SA but that has not translated to any substantial policy and language and literacy paradigm shift.

With no clear level and measurement of proficiency, lecturers in English studies perceive their role as that of teaching proficiency without a guiding policy that defines the measure or level of an EMI and English language learning. Left to the interpretation of mainly first language speakers, e.g., ‘native speakerism’ (cf. Chaka 2021; Tupas, 2022), proficiency is then based on individual beliefs and epistemicides of linguisticism and nativism, including instrumentalization of language skills. The instrumentalization of language as if it does not include culture and race is part of epistemic injustice. In Table 1 below, I illustrate how content and language are framed in some of the modules that are taught in the Bachelor of Arts (BA) Degree with a major in English Studies. There are 10 modules in the program. I mention only two below. Most of the outcomes in almost all 10 BA modules have to do with proficiency—for example, Table 1 below:

Table 1
Bachelor of Arts in English Third Year Modules

Module Title	Outcomes/Course objectives
A. The History and Spread of English	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Students are able to articulate an informed and considered position on the power and status of English nationally and internationally. 2. Students are able to integrate secondary critical source material into their discussions in a scholarly manner. 3. Students correctly employ accepted conventions of English academic discourse.
B. The English Language: Context and Purpose	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Students can engage with debates around English language use in relation to context and purpose. 2. Students can integrate secondary critical source material into their discussions in a scholarly manner. 3. Students can correctly employ accepted conventions of English academic discourse.

The key weaknesses in proficiency are the lack of measurements, lack of definition, and the vague ideological definitions that are based on the myth of perfection. All these are evident in module (A) outcomes—e.g., ‘articulate’, ‘integrate’, ‘correctly employ accepted conventions of English—all foreground a type of ‘proficiency’ that is constructed and constituted by what the academics view as ‘language’, as ‘content’, and as curriculum. In module B, a different module title is given but the outcomes are similar to those observed in Module A. The only difference is in the vaguely given, or neutrally chosen (instrumentalization) of words such as ‘context’ and ‘purpose’ which can refer to anything that is taught including a Eurocentric ‘history and spread’ of English. This is not merely an overlap in the focus or area of content identified but is symptomatic of a narrow focus on some abstract, instrumental, universalistic conceptualization of the teaching of the English language and of the dominant hegemonic influence of a narrowly conceived EMI. This shows the coloniality of language and the colonial influence of the EMI. There are many absences here, that should at least inform some of these outcomes, such as multilingualism, South African/African history or context, identity, technology, and so on. What is shown above is ‘the language of mastery’ (Singh, 2017) and the coloniality of language (cf. Chaka, 2021; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2022a, 2022b).

In the context of Unisa, proficiency in English is the only topic or content presented in a number of outcomes of the modules listed above. Therefore, this compromises the discipline. Proficiency in English can be taught without any reference to disciplines and even to academic literacy because proficiency is generic. In fact, proficiency in English is also described as general English language, and English skills. Proficiency is often depicted through neoliberal skills-based education (e.g., Holborow, 2018). For example, Kubota (2017) asserts that the skills discourse is part of human capacity and a neoliberal ideology. Therefore, the lack of a precise definition and measurement of proficiency is a recipe for English hegemony, neoliberal ideologies of ‘generic skills’, and ultimately epistemic injustice and colonial ideologies which influences ELT. In Table 1 above, the instrumental and neoliberal views about English Language proficiency resulted in the creation of the outcomes. These views are ideological and ontological myths of language in the curriculum and are not beneficial to the discipline but do serve the interest of an EMI policy.

Table 1 above, and my analysis, shows that the conceptualization of proficiency in the discipline is based on decontextualization, English monolingualism, and epistemic injustice. This shows that both black and white academics are complicit in this form of epistemicide. Tollefson (2007) observes that the route to English proficiency is widely believed to mean “English-only” without scientific evidence to back this claim but only by using ideological assumptions which “serve to blind ELT professionals to the social, economic, and political

consequences of English-only practices” (p. 27). With reference to standard English norms which are always Eurocentric based, Tollefson (2007) argues that “ELT is largely unaffected by sociolinguistics, as all sociolinguists agree that variation is normal, necessary, and intrinsic to all language varieties, including standard language” (p. 30). Therefore, sociolinguistic competence is overlooked altogether in the discipline and in policy making.

6. What should Language proficiency entail?

ELP has to be reconceptualized through the onto-epistemologies of the South so that it can be equitable to other languages. Multilingual students find themselves dehumanized through the exclusion of other languages in favour of English-Only (Phyak, 2021). Klapwik and Van der Walt (2016) observe that university students invest considerable effort in learning English, but not to the exclusion of their home language and with little desire to assimilate with the English culture. Spencer (2019) argues that there is a need to acknowledge the linguistic resources of the multilingual learner of English.

The English monolingual normative views tend to base ELP on native speakerism and Anglocentric views on generic skills. Canagarajah and Said (2010) have indicated that there is no universal standard of proficiency and that “expertise is gained through social practice, and that all of us are relative experts or novices in different varieties of English” (p. 166). Moreover, Canagarajah (2013) defines proficiency as “the ability to shuttle between different varieties of English and different speech communities” (p. 6). This definition is based on the existence of a variety, and a speech community. I define language proficiency as constituted by many competencies, including multimodal, multicompetences, multilingual competences, transmodal and translanguaging competencies all having a bearing on English and speech communities.

It follows from the above that there are various norms, and competencies that are based on different varieties. I view these as part of an English multilingual competence. Hemphill and Blakely (2019, p. 223) state that:

. . . multilingual competence emerges out of local practices where multiple languages are negotiated for communication; competence does not consist of separate competences for each language, but a multicompetence; and proficiency is about hybrid repertoire building rather than total mastery of each and every language.

Despite this fact, colonial hierarchies persist, and academic English language norms are valued by the ‘center’. These norms exclude the linguistic resources and linguistic repertoires of students (cf. García and Lin, 2018). The various

multilingual norms and multicompetences should then reconstitute English *multilingua franca*.

An English as a *multilingua franca* should be both dynamic and contextualized in SA. It is a departure from some of the established traditions, such as, ELT, TESOL, ELF, WE, and EAL because they all carry epistemic injustices. Other versions of English like ELF also perpetuate the myth, and are not in line with a view of multilingualism as a *lingua franca* (see, Makoni & Pennycook, 2012). Saraceni (2009) argues that the spread of English in the world necessitates a paradigm shift in ELT. He observes that there are pitfalls in nomenclatures such as World Englishes (WE), country-based Englishes, and ELF (cf. Pennycook, 2020). Pennycook (2020) argues that neither World Englishes nor English as a *Lingua Franca* are equivalent to decolonization. This critique of many of the fields that traditionally fall under English Studies calls for alternative epistemologies, as mentioned above.

Many changes in the configuration of English curricula are still based on Western (North)centric epistemologies by following mainstream models such as World Englishes (WE) and so called Second Language Acquisition (SLA). Both the scholarship on WE and SLA, two leading fields in the postcolonial Africa have failed to deliver any decolonization because of their heavy orientation to monolingualism, native vs. non-native, assessment regimes and so on (cf. Ortega, 2018). Decolonizing should rather focus on “how English resources may be part of multilingual repertoires” (García & Lin, 2018, p. 98). This is what I am proposing with English as a *multilingua franca* in education below.

The onto-epistemic focus on ELP will also impact on the EMI. Pennycook and Makoni (2020) observe that a focus on language in education foregrounds contentious issues of the medium of instruction in schools and universities. They argue that the matter is not going to be resolved by replacing English with an indigenous language. It requires reconceptualising educational multilingualism, southern multilingualism from the time of transition from home to primary school, from orality to writing and therefore finding alternatives to monolingualism. What is needed is a radical change such as ‘English *multilingua franca*’ and ‘Ubuntu-Neplanta’ through a reclamation of both multilingualism-within English, and decolonization strategies such as ‘border thinking’ (Cushman, 2016), and not the canonical western centric logic of ‘interpretation’ found in many English Studies courses. Border thinking is the state of inbetweenness that has been proposed above under onto-epistemological approaches, and is illustrated below in a solidarity-based epistemology. Meighan (2021) identifies some of the epistemic errors in English and makes a proposal for implementing alternative ways of knowing and being in education in order to decolonize English.

7. Towards decolonizing EMI and ELP: English as a multilingua franca and Ubuntu-Nepantla

I, therefore, call for a rethinking and a re-imagining of EMI and ELP which is both decolonial and transformative. It has been foregrounded above that a new metalanguage will have to be introduced both in EMI and English Language proficiency. Decoloniality refers to ways of knowing, thinking, doing, and being that undo structures of race, class, heteropatriarchy, and gender, which tend to exercise control over knowledge, thought, spirituality, and life in accordance with Western modernity and global capitalism (Chaka et al., 2022). In my view, onto-epistemic approaches to a decolonised English enables academics to redefine the syllabus, content, EMI, for the context of ODeL, in order to promote access, inclusion, and epistemic justice.

In the proposed reconceptualization of proficiency, the relationship between Multilingualism and English is displayed through English as a multilingua franca in order to reshape both EMI and ELP. Scholars have noted that multilingualism is a lingua franca of Africa (Fardon & Furniss 1994; as cited in Makoni, 2020). Ishikawa (2021) explains translanguaging and English-within-multilingualism in the Japanese EMI. English cannot be separated from the milieu of the sociolinguistic and multilingual context. This does not mean replacing English language with African languages or plural monolingualism (Pennycook & Makoni 2020). In short, Ishikawa (2021) explains that EMF “views English as embedded in wider multilingual, multicultural, and multimodal resources as well as effectuated through translanguaging, transcultural, and transmodal processes” (p. 39).⁴

Monolingualism, epistemic racism, and the epistemicides that have been mentioned above are some of the problems brought by coloniality. I have illustrated that coloniality comes with the norms and prestige varieties that exclude additional and multilingual speakers of English. Proficiency has to address both EMF and EMI (Ishikawa, 2021), unlike the situation at present where both academics in English Studies and academics belonging to the wider university community agree that English proficiency is important but use Anglocentric definitions and do not relate proficiency to the current sociolinguistic realities and the institutional EMI. Similarly, Ishikawa (2021) is interested in ELT and EMI programs in Japan. He takes a theoretical stance from ELF but applies it to translanguaging, multimodality and technology. He explains how meaning making is construed in EMI abbreviations but also how this is translated to pedagogy, curriculum and policies in higher education. His focus on the distinction between language, multilingual resources, practices and constructs enables his work to address proficiency in English but also broadly the status of English in the discipline, and English communication for students, academics and the world. In my view, EMF is more relevant because

it deals with power, ideology, codes and so on but also the broader field of multilingualism, and communication, something which cannot be reduced to WE, EAL or ESL.

8. Conclusion

This article is presented as a meta reflection, which limits itself to the position of academics. However, decoloniality is a complex process that involves national politics, government who fund public universities, parents, students and so on.

I conclude with a manifesto based on two main agenda setting actions for academics in order to undo the coloniality of language and EMI, and attain epistemic justice. These can be labelled as (1) English as a Multilingua Franca, and (2) an Onto-epistemic paradigm (Ubuntu-Nepantla). They represent a kind of manifesto that has been advocated by decolonial scholars (e.g., García et al. 2021; Santos, 2020)—in other words, a call to ‘action’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2023a).

The type of English language proficiency that is required in SA is one that will demystify and demythologize both EMI and proficiency. English should be taught in a multilingual approach. An English department that seeks to open access to, and address, inequalities of languages and opportunities for 11 official languages has to teach for diversity and multilingualism. This will have to go beyond the bilingual approach that García et al. (2021) describe in Canada. Students should be able to navigate different varieties of English and affirm their multilingual practices through English as a multilingua franca. This should move away from asking binary questions of language choice which end up promoting monolingualism. This is in line with disinventing and reconstituting languages (cf. Makoni & Pennycook, 2007).

Presently, teaching skills like reading, speaking, writing, and listening are divorced from theories of language, languaging, and multilingualism (Holborow, 2018; Kubota, 2017; Sebolai, 2016). Instead, a neoliberal discourse that comes from managers and administrators, relegates the English Department to a service department and does not recognize research and scholarship in the field. The scholarship of theory and practice in language teaching should inform the status of English within multilingualism and the EMI policy. Universities are good at designing policies that meet the requirement of the constitution and governmental institutions, while they carry on with an unwritten EMI policy and epistemicides under the disguise of English language proficiency.

Academics need to engage in an onto-epistemic analysis of the content and syllabus. Santos, (2020) highlights the importance of language in decolonizing

the curriculum and focusing on the ecologies of knowledge. I have illustrated some of the intellectual contestations that have to accompany an approach to decolonial entanglements in SA, at Unisa. The Western Imperial English epistemes have dominated English Language Teaching through approaches such as WE, ESL, ESP, EFL, and so on. These Euro-American approaches have come with teaching materials, publishers, and enforced beliefs in native speakerism, epistemic injustices, racism and standard English. For many decades, academics have simply accepted these as sacrosanct and not questioned their suitability. Decoloniality should include thinking otherwise in order to undo coloniality of theory and practice—EMI policy with the ELP curriculum. At Unisa, the content, titles, outcomes, and assessment criteria in a module are very important because they are designed by teams and get approved by the institutional structures all the way to the Department of Higher Education which governs all public national universities. An onto-epistemic paradigm is desirable in order to approach institutional and educational policies that inform curriculum and qualifications that are governed by the DHET. Connell (2018) proposes the use of mosaic epistemology and solidarity-based epistemology in order to decolonise sociology; likewise, in this paper, I propose Ubuntu-Nepantla. All in all, a mosaic epistemology is required to decolonize our language and educational policies.

Notes:

1. Discussions of meaning are very delicate; for a good introduction, see Salmani Nodoushan (2022).
2. For a brief overview of reflective teaching, see Salmani Nodoushan (2011).
3. See Salmani Nodoushan (2016).
4. For more on translanguaging and other relevant topics including diversity, equity, multilingualism, decolonisation epistemologies, social justice, activism, and so forth, please see Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Hannaford and Alexander (2024), Huang (2024). Kruger-Marias (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), Xu and Fang (2024).

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